

Bivariate BCI Algebras

E. Ilojide^{1*} and O. O. George²

1. Department of Mathematics, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta 110101, Nigeria.
* Corresponding author: emmailojide@yahoo.com*, ilojidee@funaab.edu.ng
2. Department of Mathematics, University of Lagos, Akoka, Nigeria.
femi_george@yahoo.co.uk, oogeorge@unilag.edu.ng

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Abstract

In this paper, the concept of bivariate BCI algebras is introduced. Properties of ρ -variate, λ -variate and bivariate BCI algebras are investigated.

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1 Introduction

An algebra of type $(2, 0)$ is a non-empty set, having a constant element, on which is defined a binary operation such that certain axioms are satisfied. BCI algebras and BCK algebras, introduced in [16] and [15], are common varieties of such algebras. There are several other varieties of algebras of type $(2, 0)$. There are also several generalizations of BCI algebras. In [5], BCH algebras were studied. In [22], d algebras were studied. In [19], the notion of BE algebras was introduced. Ideals and upper sets in BE algebras were investigated in [1] and [2]. Pre-commutative algebras were studied in [20]. Fenyves algebras were studied in [17], [13] and [18]. Recently, it has been shown in [3] that algebras of type $(2,0)$ have diverse applications in coding theory. Motivated by this, more research interest has been given to the study of algebras of type $(2,0)$. In [21], Q algebras were introduced. Nayo algebras were studied in [7]. Obic algebras were introduced and properties of implicative obic algebras were investigated in [8]. In [9], torian algebras were studied. It was shown that the class of torian algebras is a wider class than the class of obic algebras.

In this paper, bivariate BCI algebras are introduced. Properties of ρ -variate, λ -variate and bivariate BCI algebras are investigated.

2 Preliminaries

In this section, some basic concepts necessary for proper understanding of this paper are discussed.

Definition 2.1. [16]. An algebra $(X; *, 0)$; where X is a non-empty set, $*$ a binary operation defined on X , and 0 a constant element of X is called a BCI algebra if the following hold for all $x, y, z \in X$:

1. $((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0$
2. $(x * (x * y)) * y = 0$
3. $x * x = 0$
4. $x * y = 0, y * x = 0 \Rightarrow x = y$
5. $x * 0 = x$

Define a binary relation \leq on a BCI algebra $(X; *, 0)$ by $x \leq y$ if and only if $x * y = 0$. Then $(X; \leq)$ is a partially ordered set.

Definition 2.2. [16]. A BCI algebra $(X; *, 0)$ which satisfies $0 * x = 0$ for all $x \in X$ is called a BCK algebra.

Proposition 2.3. [23]. Let x, y, z be elements of a BCI algebra X . Then $x \leq y \Rightarrow z * y \leq z * x$.

Definition 2.4. Let X be a BCI algebra. We define $x * y^k = [(x * y) * y] * \dots * y$ (k times); where k is a natural number.

The following Lemmas are straightforward from definition.

Lemma 2.5. Let X be a BCI algebra. Then $x * (x * (x * y)) = x * y$ for all $x, y \in X$.

Lemma 2.6. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCI algebra. Then $(x * y) * z = (x * z) * y$ for all $x, y, z \in X$.

We shall denote a BCI algebra by X unless there is the need to emphasize its binary operation and the constant element.

3 Main Results

In this section, we introduce ρ - variate, λ - variate and bivariate BCI algebras and some of their properties are investigated.

Definition 3.1. Let X be a BCI algebra. An element $x \in X$ is called a ρ - variate element if $(y * z) * x = (y * x) * (z * x)$ for all $y, z \in X$.

The collection of all ρ - variate elements of X is denoted by X^ρ . If $X^\rho = X$, then X is called a ρ - variate BCI algebra.

Definition 3.2. Let X be a BCI algebra. An element $x \in X$ is called a λ - variate element if $x * (y * z) = (x * y) * (x * z)$ for all $y, z \in X$.

The collection of all λ - variate elements of X is denoted by X^λ . Notice that $X^\lambda \neq X$ for any BCI algebra X .

Definition 3.3. An element x in a BCI algebra X , is called a bivariate element if x is both λ - variate and ρ - variate.

Proposition 3.4. Let X be a BCI algebra. Then 0 is a bivariate element of X .

Proof. Let $x, y \in X$. Then $(0 * x) * (0 * y) = (((x * y) * (x * y)) * x) * (0 * y) = (((x * y) * x) * (x * y)) * (0 * y) = ((0 * y) * (x * y)) * (0 * y) = 0 * (x * y)$. Thus, 0 is λ - variate. The fact that 0 is ρ - variate is obvious. \square

Definition 3.5. A BCI algebra X is called a bivariate BCI algebra if the following hold:

- 1 . X is a ρ - variate;
- 2 . $\{0\} \subset X^\lambda$.

Example 3.6. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$. Define a binary operation $*$ on X by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	0	0
2	2	2	0	2	0
3	3	3	3	0	0
4	4	4	3	2	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a bivariate BCI algebra. Notice that $\{0\} \neq X^\lambda \cap X^\rho$ because $2 \in X^\lambda \cap X^\rho$.

The following Lemma is obvious from definition.

Lemma 3.7. Let X be a ρ -variate BCI algebra. Then the following hold for all $x, y, z \in X$:

- 1 . $y * x = (y * x) * (0 * x)$;
- 2 . $0 * x = 0$;
- 3 . $(x * z) * x = 0 * (z * x)$;
- 4 . $0 * z = 0 * (z * x)$;
- 5 . $(y * z) * z = y * z$;
- 6 . $(y * x) * z = y * z$;
- 7 . $((0 * x) * z) * x = ((0 * x) * x) * (z * x)$;
- 8 . $(y * x) = (y * x) * ((0 * x) * x)$;
- 9 . $(x * z) * x = (0 * x) * (z * x)$;
- 10 . $(0 * x) * z = (0 * x) * (z * x)$;
- 11 . $(x * z) * x = 0$.

Theorem 3.8. Let X be a BCI algebra. Then X is ρ -variate if and only if $x * y = (x * y) * y$ for all $x, y \in X$.

Proof. Suppose $x * y = (x * y) * y$ for all $x, y \in X$. Notice that $(x * z) * (y * z) = ((x * z) * z) * (y * z) \leq (x * z) * y$. So,

$$((x * z) * (y * z)) * ((x * z) * y) = 0 \tag{1}$$

By Lemma 3.1(11), we have $(y * z) \leq y$. By Proposition 2.1, we have $(x * z) * y \leq (x * z) * (y * z)$. Therefore,

$$((x * z) * y) * ((x * z) * (y * z)) = 0 \tag{2}$$

From expressions (1) and (2), we have $(x * z) * y = (x * z) * (y * z)$ or, equivalently, $(x * y) * z = (x * z) * (y * z)$ as required.

By Lemma 3.1(5), the converse holds. □

Corollary 3.9. Let X be a BCI algebra. Then X is ρ -variate if and only if $(x * y) * y = x * (x * (x * y))$ for all $x, y \in X$.

Proof. This follows from Theorem 3.1 and the fact that $x * (x * (x * y)) = x * y$ for all $x, y \in X$. □

Theorem 3.10. Let X be a ρ -variate BCI algebra such that the following hold for all $x, y, z, p, v \in X$:

1. $(x * (y * z)) * (x * (y * p)) \leq (z * p)$;
2. $x \leq y \Rightarrow (z * y) \leq (z * x)$;
3. $(x * y) \leq v \Rightarrow (x * v) \leq (x * (x * y))$.

Then $(x * (x * y)) * (y * x) = (x * x * (y * (y * x)))$ for all $x, y \in X$.

Proof. Notice that $[x * (x * y)] * [x * [x * [y * (y * x)]]] \leq [y * [y * (y * x)]] = y * x$. Hence, $[x * (x * y)] * (y * x) \leq [x * [x * [y * (y * x)]]]$. Now let $[x * [y * (y * x)]] = v$. Then we have $(x * v) \leq [y * (y * x)]$. Notice that $[y * (y * x)] \leq y$. So, $(x * y) \leq [x * [y * (y * x)]]$; giving us $(x * y) \leq v$; so that $(x * v) \leq [x * (x * y)]$. Now notice also that $[y * (y * x)] = [y * (y * x)] * (y * x) \leq [x * (y * x)]$. Since $(x * v) \leq [y * (y * x)]$ and $[y * (y * x)] \leq [x * (y * x)]$, we have $(x * v) \leq [x * (y * x)]$.

Now, 'multiply' both sides of the last relation on the right by v to get $[(x * v) * v] \leq [x * (y * x)] * v$. That is, $[(x * v) * v] \leq (x * v) * (y * x)$; giving us $(x * v) \leq [(x * v) * (y * x)]$; leading to $(x * v) \leq [[x * (x * y)] * (y * x)]$. Substituting back for v , we have $[x * [x * [y * (y * x)]]] \leq [x * (x * y)] * (y * x)$. Since $[x * (x * y)] * (y * x) \leq [x * [x * [y * (y * x)]]]$ and $[x * [x * [y * (y * x)]]] \leq [x * (x * y)] * (y * x)$, we conclude that $[x * [x * [y * (y * x)]]] = [x * (x * y)] * (y * x)$ as required. \square

Corollary 3.11. Let X be a bivariate BCI algebra such that the following hold for all $x, y, z, p, v \in X^\lambda$:

1. $((x * y) * (x * z)) * ((x * y) * (x * p)) \leq (z * p)$;
2. $x \leq y \Rightarrow z * (y * x) = 0$;
3. $(x * y) \leq v \Rightarrow (x * v) * (0 * (x * y)) = 0$.

Then $(x * (x * (0 * (x * y)))) = (0 * (x * y)) * (y * x)$ for all $x, y \in X^\lambda$.

Proof. It follows from Theorem 3.2 and the definition of X^λ . \square

Corollary 3.12. Let X be a ρ -variate BCI algebra such that the following hold for all $x, y, z, p, v \in X$:

1. $(x * (y * z)) * (x * (y * p)) \leq (z * p)$;
2. $x \leq y \Rightarrow (z * y) \leq (z * x)$;
3. $(x * y) \leq v \Rightarrow (x * v) \leq (x * (x * y))$.

Then $(x * (y * x)) * ((x * y) * (y * x)) = (x * (x * (y * (y * x))))$ for all $x, y \in X$.

Proof. It follows from Theorem 3.2 and the definition of X^ρ . \square

Theorem 3.13. Let X be a ρ -variate BCI algebra such that the following hold for all $x, y, z, p, v \in X$:

1. $(x * (y * z)) * (x * (y * p)) \leq (z * p)$;
2. $x \leq y \Rightarrow (z * y) \leq (z * x)$;
3. $(x * y) \leq v \Rightarrow (x * v) \leq (x * (x * y))$.

Then $(x * y) * (x * (x * y)) = x * y$ for all $x, y \in X$.

Proof. By Theorem 3.2, for all $x, y \in X$, we have

$$[x * (x * y)] * (y * x) = [x * [x * [y * (y * x)]]] \quad (3)$$

Put $x * y$ for x , and put x for y in expression (1). Then the left hand side becomes $[(x * y) * [(x * y) * x]] * [x * (x * y)]$
 $= [(x * y) * [(x * x) * y]] * [x * (x * y)] = [(x * y) * (0 * y)] * [x * (x * y)]$

= (x * y) * [x * (x * y)].

Also, the right hand side becomes (x * y) * [(x * y) * [x * [x * (x * y)]]]

= (x * y) * [(x * y) * (x * y)] = x * y.

Hence, equating the left and right hand sides, we have (x * y) * [x * (x * y)] = x * y as required. □

Corollary 3.14. Let X be a bivariate BCI algebra such that the following hold for all x, y, z, p, v in X^λ:

- 1. ((x * y) * (x * z)) * ((x * y) * (x * p)) ≤ (z * p);
- 2. x ≤ y ⇒ z * (y * x) = 0;
- 3. (x * y) ≤ v ⇒ (x * v) * (0 * (x * y)) = 0.

Then (x * y) * (x * (x * y)) = x * y for all x, y ∈ X^λ.

Proof. It follows from Theorem 3.3 and the definition of X^λ. □

Corollary 3.15. Let X be a ρ- variate BCI algebra such that the following hold for all x, y, z, p, v ∈ X:

- 1. (x * (y * z)) * (x * (y * p)) ≤ (z * p);
- 2. x ≤ y ⇒ (z * y) ≤ (z * x);
- 3. (x * y) ≤ v ⇒ (x * v) ≤ (x * (x * y)).

Then (x * (x * (x * y))) * ((y * x) * (x * y)) = x * y for all x, y ∈ X.

Proof. It follows from Theorem 3.3 and the definition of X^ρ. □

Theorem 3.16. Let X be a ρ- variate BCI algebra such that the following hold for all x, y, z ∈ X:

- 1. x ≤ y ⇒ (x * z) ≤ (y * z)
- 2. x * y^k = x * y^{k+1}; where k ∈ ℕ; the set of natural numbers.
- 3. x * y^k = x * y^l for all l ≥ k ∈ ℕ
- 4. (x * z^k) * (y * z^k) ≤ (x * y).

Then (x * y) * z^k = (x * z^k) = (x * z^k) * (y * z^k) for all x, y, z ∈ X.

Proof. By hypothesis, we have x * z^k = x * z^{2k}. Since, (x * z^k) * (y * z^k) ≤ (x * y), we have [(x * z^k) * (y * z^k)] * z^k ≤ (x * y) * z^k; which gives [(x * z^k) * z^k] * (y * z^k) ≤ (x * y) * z^k; which results to (x * z^{2k}) * (y * z^k) ≤ (x * y) * z^k. Since x * z^k = x * z^{2k}, we now have

$$(x * z^k) * (y * z^k) ≤ (x * y) * z^k \tag{4}$$

Notice that (y * z^k) * y = 0. So, (y * z^k) ≤ y. We therefore have [(x * z^k) * y] ≤ [(x * z^k) * (y * z^k)]; which gives

$$[(x * y) * z^k] ≤ [(x * z^k) * (y * z^k)] \tag{5}$$

By expressions (4) and (5), we have (x * y) * z^k = (x * z^k) * (y * z^k) as required. □

Proposition 3.17. Let X be a ρ- variate BCI algebra. If (x * y) * z^k = (x * z^k) * (y * z^k), then x * z^k = x * z^{k+1} for all x, y, z ∈ X; k ∈ ℕ.

Proof. By hypothesis, we have (x * z) * z^k = (x * z^k) * (z * z^k); which gives x * z^{k+1} = x * z^k as required. □

Theorem 3.18. Let X be a ρ- variate BCI algebra such that the following hold for all x, y, z ∈ X:

1. $x * y^k = x * y^{k+1}, k \in \mathbb{N};$
2. $x * y^k = x * y^l$ for all $l \geq k;$
3. $x \leq y \Rightarrow (x * z) * (y * z).$

Then $[y * (y * x)^k] * (x * y)^k = [x * (x * y)^k] * (y * x)^k$ for all $x, y \in X.$

Proof. By hypothesis, we have

$$x * (x * y)^{k_1} = x * (x * y)^{k_1} \quad (6)$$

and

$$y * (y * x)^{k_2} = y * (y * x)^{k_2} \quad (7)$$

Let k be the maximum of k_1 and $k_2.$ Then

$$x * (x * y)^k = x * (x * y)^{k+1} \quad (8)$$

and

$$y * (y * x)^k = y * (y * x)^{k+1} \quad (9)$$

Notice that $[x * (x * y)] * y = 0.$ So, $x * (x * y) \leq y;$ and from expression (6), we have

$$x * [(x * y)^k] \leq y * (x * y)^k \quad (10)$$

Now, 'multiply' expression (8) on both sides on the right by $y * x$ (k times) to get

$$[x * (x * y)^k] * (y * x)^k \sim [y * (x * y)^k] * (y * x)^k \quad (11)$$

Now apply Lemma 2.2 to expression (9) to get

$$[x * (x * y)^k] * (y * x)^k \sim [y * (y * x)^k] * (x * y)^k \quad (12)$$

Also notice that $[y * (y * x)] * x = 0.$ So, $[y * (y * x)] \leq x;$ and so from expression (7), we have

$$[y * (y * x)^k] \leq [x * (y * x)^k] \quad (13)$$

'Multiply' both sides of expression (11) on the right by $x * y$ (k times) to get

$$[y * (y * x)^k] * (x * y)^k \leq [x * (y * x)^k] * (x * y)^k \quad (14)$$

Now apply Lemma 2.2 to expression (12) to get

$$[y * (y * x)^k] * (x * y)^k \leq [x * (x * y)^k] * (y * x)^k \quad (15)$$

From expressions (12) and (15), we have $[y * (y * x)^k] * (x * y)^k$
 $= [x * (x * y)^k] * (y * x)^k$ as required. \square

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